

Article

Design and Analysis of Microstrip Patch Antenna for WLAN & WiMax Applications using Parametric Analysis

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A B S T R A C T

This paper presents a novel design of microstrip patch antenna for WLAN, WiMax & HyperLAN applications by using quarter transform to get good impedance match by using simple inset fed, it will improve the bandwidth, return loss, gain and radiation characteristic. The recommended model designed and optimized by assigning variables to each components of model. The patch antenna was analyzed using Ansoft/ Ansys HFSS and made a comparison by using variable length at two different fed length of inset feed point. The proposed antenna works better for applications like microwave system operating at WLAN (2.4-5.2GHz) and Hyper LAN (5.725-5.825) band of frequencies.

Keywords: FR4 Epoxy Substrate, Scattering Matrix, VSWR, Inset Fed, Qw Transform

Introduction

In current correspondence frameworks, the utilization of Microstrip Receiving Wires (MSAs) has become far and wide due to their alluring properties, for example, planar, light weight, low profile, low creation cost, and so forth Yet, the fundamental limits of MSAs are their tight impedance data transfer capacity and lower acquire which is due to the resonant characteristics of the patch structure. But on the other hand advanced communication systems, such as those for Wireless Local Area Networks (WLAN), just as arising applications, for example, satellite connections (vehicular, GPS and so forth) frequently require receiving wires with minimal effort and smallness, hence requiring planar innovation. Because of the light weight of the microstrip patch antennas.

Due to these utilizations of the microstrip fix receiving wire, another inspiration is advanced for innovative work on native arrangements that defeat the transfer

speed impediments of the fix reception apparatuses. In applications in which data transmission upgrade is needed for the activity of two separate sub-groups, a fitting option in contrast to the widening of the all-out transfer speed is addressed by double recurrence microstrip receiving wire, which displays a double resounding conduct in a solitary emanating component.

The most well-known technique for generating a dual-frequency behavior in the single-fed microstrip antenna is to establish reactive loadings in the radiating element. The easiest way to do so is to create or etch slots on the radiating element of the microstrip patch antenna. The slot loading in the radiating patch creates a strong modification of the resonant modes, particularly when the slots are configured to obstruct and cut the current lines of the unperturbed modes. Example in,¹ The square microstrip patch antenna² provides dual band operation with a rectangular notch along the radiating edge. Two

rectangular slots are created³ in parallel with the two radiating edges of the rectangular patch for the dual-frequency operation. In,⁴ two rectangular slots are etched along the two radiating edges of the rectangular patch and were fed by an aperture, coupled to the radiating element. In,⁵ two rectangular slots are taken out from the rectangular glowing element, are placed in parallel to the two radiating edges of the patch and fed by a coaxial feed to have the dual-band operation of the microstrip patch antenna. In,⁶ the reactive loading is provided by a structure of two cascaded microstrip-line sections embedded within a rectangular slot cut in the patch. By selecting suitable dimensions of the microstrip-line sections and the rectangular slot, dual-frequency operation can be obtained. In,⁷ the slots loaded in the patch are a pair of outward bent slots centered in the rectangular microstrip patch and oriented along the resonant direction, with the spacing between the two slots being about half the patch's radiating-edge length, a dual-frequency operation has obtained. multi-band printed antenna for an application in WLAN.

Based on the background of the structures of various dual-frequency microstrip antennas above, this paper proposes a combination of quarter wave transform and of simple inset-fed for better impedance matching to get better band width and return loss for dual frequency microstrip antenna having a rectangular slot on the radiating element. The dual-frequency operation of the proposed antenna is achieved by etching a rectangular slot on the top of radiating element. The planned antenna is fed by 50-Ω microstrip transmission line with Quarter wave transform and the fed is inserted into the radiating patch element for the proper impedance matching. The proposed dual-frequency inset-fed microstrip antenna resonates at 3.5167 GHz , 4.233 GHz , 4.500GHz, and 5.5833-5.8867 GHz for 22.7361 to 17.012 dB return loss. The frequency ratios of the two operating frequencies are tunable in the range of about 3.5167, 5.5833 - 5.8867 GHz. the operating band of wireless local area networks (WLAN) & HyperLAN.

In this paper, a simple dual-frequency by using quarter wave and conventional inset-fed microstrip antenna with a rectangular slot for the application in the WLAN & HyperLAN

Basic Charecteristics

The microstrip antenna apparatus appeared in figure1 comprises of flimsy ($t \ll \lambda_0$, where λ_0 is the free-space frequency) metallic strip (fix) put a little part of a frequency ($h \ll \lambda_0$, typically $0.003\lambda_0 \leq h \leq 0.05\lambda_0$) over a ground plane. The microstrip fix is required so its example most extreme is typical to the fix (broadside radiator). This is cultivated via cautiously picking the mode (field arrangement) of excitation underneath the fix. End fire radiation can likewise be cultivated by sensible mode choice. For a rectangular fix, the length of L of the component is typically $\lambda_0/3 < L$

$< \lambda_0/2$. The strip (fix) and the ground plane are isolated by a dielectric sheet (alluded to as the substrate) as demonstrated in figure 1.

Figure 1. Inset fed

For designing of microstrip antennas^{8,9} there are numerous substrates, whose dielectric constants are in the range of $2.2 \leq \epsilon_r < 12$. The ones that are most wanted for good antenna presentation are thick substrates whose dielectric constant is near about the lower range because they provide better efficiency, larger bandwidth, loosely bound fields for radiation into space, but at the expense of larger element size. Thin substrates with higher dielectric constants are alluring for microwave hardware since they require firmly bound fields to limit undesired radiation and coupling and lead to more modest component sizes; be that as it may, on account of their more prominent misfortunes, they are less proficient and have moderately more modest data transmission. Since miniature strip receiving wires¹⁰ are frequently coordinated with other microwave hardware, a trade off should be reached between acceptable radio wire execution and circuit plan. In the following area the taking care of strategy is examined

Feeding Method

Figure 2. Quarter wave transform fed

The recommended antennas are designed using low cost glass epoxy substrate material of thickness, $h = 1.66$ mm

and dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 4.2$. The artwork of proposed antennas is developed using computer software Auto CAD-2006 to attain healthier precision. The antennas are fabricated using photolithography process.

Figure 2, shows the geometry of conventional Rectangular Microstrip Antenna (RMSA). The antenna is designed for the resonant frequency of 2.4 GHz. It comprises of radiating patch of length L and width W , quarter wave transformer of length L_t and width W_t used for better impedance matching between the patch and 50Ω feed line of length L_f and width W_f .

Due impedance disparity it's not resonating with acceptable return loss to overcome this by simple inset feed is combined with quarter wave transform in proposed model to get work at WLAN, WIMAX & HyperLAN with better return loss and bandwidth.

Antenna Design and Result

The design question of rectangular microstrip patch antenna is calculated using equation.^{11,12} Antenna is given below Figure 3. Proposed antenna design Where L = length of the patch W = width of the patch Y_0 = distance where the impedance is 50Ω of quarter wave transform optimized by assigning variable $Sl=0.01$ to 1.00 step size = 0.01 , by result of active $S(1,1)$ parameter at $sl=0.84$ and 0.97 by comparing result $sl=0.84$ will get good result in RL, BW, radiation pattern.

Table 1. Quarter wave transform fed

$L = 29.4424$ mm	$W = 38.0363$ mm
$L_t = 15.1334$ mm	$W_t = 0.50$ mm
$L_f = 15.0060$ mm	$W_f = 3.0590$ mm
$L_t = 15.1334$ mm	$W_t = 0.50$ mm
Substrate	$L_s=L+6g, w_s=W+6h$
Height of substrate	$h=1.6$

Figure 3. Proposed antenna Model of Micro-Strip Patch antenna QW& Inset feed in HFSS (TopView)

Figure 4. Proposed antenna model cross sectional view by using inset fed of depth sl

Figure 5. Proposed antenna model by using inset fed of depth $sl=0.84$

After all calculation, the antenna designed in HFSS software. In design of antenna by assigning variable to component such as patch, substrate, feed line, source port, radiation box it gives advantages if change in small value it will effect to whole dimensions of the module so in proposed module by assigning by simple inset feed length sl used by using parametric optimization at $sl=0.84$ as compare to $sl=0.97$ gives better results as shown below.

Result

In these section results of proposed work depicted.

When the modelling of the proposed antenna is completed in HFSS, the following results are obtained. From Figure. 6 & 7, it is depicted that the designed antenna at $sl=0.84$ inset fed is providing return loss of $-4.2549, -17.8882, -16.5620, -17.2816$ dB at at the resonant frequencies of $2.265, 3.5167, 4.233, 4.500, 5.5833, 5.8867$ GHz as compare to $sl=0.97$ the return loss are $-4.323, 23.2926, -27.2162, 16.6670$ at frequencies $2.2333, 3.483, 4.2833, 5.9560$ for multi band frequency operation. At $sl=0.84$ gives better result by good impedance match, Figure 8. Depicts the 2D radiation pattern for all values of theta and phi values ranging from 0 to 90 degrees. Figure 9, depicts the 2D radiation pattern for all values of phi and theta values ranging from 0 to 90 degrees.

Figure 6. Parameter at sl=0.84

Figure 10. VSWR t at sl=0.84

Figure 7. S11 Parameter at sl=0.97

Figure 8. 2D radiation pattern for all values of theta and phi values ranging from 0 to 90 degrees

Figure 9. 3D Radiation Polar Plot at sl=0.84

Conclusion

The paper presents state of work which includes the design procedure of microstrip patch antenna by using optimization of inset fed length by assigning variable fed length between 0.01 to 1.00mm by using step size 0.01 by results of active parameter of S(1,1) of sl=0.84 and sl=0.97 of variable length, sl=0.84 gives good result as compare to sl=0.97 in bandwidth and return loss radiation pattern and VSWR also acceptable below 2dB line figure 10. The single band of RMSA can be converted into dual and triple bands by simple inset fed matching on the patch respectively. The proposed antennas are simple in their geometry and are fabricated using low cost glass epoxy substrate material. These antennas may find applications in mobile WiMax (3.4 to 3.6 GHz), HyperLAN/2 (5.725 to 5.825 GHz), cordless phones (5 GHz), fixed wireless (5 GHz), etc.

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